

Studies on the Transformation of Iron Phosphates in Buffer and Acid Soil Systems

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Chemical transformation of different iron phosphates in contact with buffer and acid soils systems at different pHs 4.8, 5.2, 5.8 and 6.2 were studied. The results indicate that these iron phosphates undergo hydrolysis reactions and basic (hydroxy) phosphates were ultimately converted to $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Such transformation were effected by different probable chemical reactions.

Hsu and Jackson⁵ observed that the transformation of iron phosphates in soils were mainly controlled by pH. Bache¹ determined solubility. Products for strengite ($\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in pure systems and stated that strengite is never likely to be in equilibrium with any soil solution. He concluded that surface reactions are likely to be responsible for the few reports of ion activity products in soils which are of the same order as that of strengite. This may explain the observation of Chakravarti and Talibudeen² who concluded that compounds approximately to the composition of strengite may occur in the temperate climate soils in the pH range 3.8 to 4.2.

Larson⁶ pointed out that co-existence of various iron, aluminium and calcium in the form of surface complex in soils is particularly likely since pH of a given soil may show considerable local variations.

The favourable and unfavourable effects of iron phosphates as fertilizers observed by McGeorge and Breazeale⁷ and Dalton *et al.*³ respectively were probably associated with chemical transformation of iron phosphates in soils.

The studies of changes of composition of iron phosphates in contact with buffer and acid soils are limited, although from phosphate fertility status determination of acid soils, these studies are important.

Experimental

Two ferric phosphates were used: (1) Purchased Fe-P, designated as Fe-P (A) from Albright and Wilson Ltd., London: Analysis gave $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 = 1:1$ corresponds to FePO_4 (2) prepared Fe-P, designated as Fe-P (B), was prepared as follows:

Ferric hydroxide was prepared from ferric chlorides washed salt free and suspended in water. Ammonium phosphates was then added and the suspension adjusted to pH 2.5 by the addition of phosphoric acids. The

resultant product was washed with water, till phosphate free and then washed with alcohol and benzene and finally dried in air at 40°. The orange brown product was lightly ground in agate mortar before use. Analysis gave $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5 : 1:2.5$. It is a mixture of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_4\text{PO}_4)$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_3$ (Gasser & Bloomfield⁴).

In order to study the transformation of iron phosphates at different pHs in buffer solutions, 0.5g samples of the two iron phosphates (Fe-P(A) & Fe-P(B)) were taken in cellophane bags with 5 ml distilled water and a few drops toluene and the bags were kept suspended by threads in 200 ml phthalate-NaOH buffer mixtures⁹ at pHs 4.8, 5.2, 5.8 and 6.2 for 6 months. The buffer mixtures also contained a few drops of toluene and the systems were subjected to occasional shaking. After the period chemical analyses were performed to determine the change in composition in the original phosphate. Iron was determined by dichromate after reduction with SnCl_2 and phosphate by ammonium molybdate precipitation followed by dissolution in NaOH and back titration with standard acid¹⁰.

In order to study the transformation of different iron phosphates at different pHs in contact with soil water suspension 20 gms samples of soils K, J, T and M (pH 4.8, 5.2, 5.8 and 6.15 respectively) were taken with 200 ml water and a few drops of toluene in stoppered bottles and 0.5 g of samples of the bottles and 0.5g of samples of the phosphates in cellophane bags with 5 ml distilled water and a few drops toluene were then allowed to come in contact with the soil-water mixtures. The mixtures were then left for 6 months for equilibrium with occasional shaking. After the period, changes in composition in the original phosphates were determined by chemical analyses as before.

The characteristics of the acid soils are tabulated in Table 1 and the changes in composition of the iron phosphate samples as shown by the ratio $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ undergone in contact with buffer and soil water suspensions are given in Tables 2 and 3 represented graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF ACID SOILS

Locality	Latitude and Longitude of the place	Family	CO ₂ effervescence with HCl	pH	Organic carbon %	C.E.C me/100 gms	% of HCl soluble		
							Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	P ₂ O ₅
1. Kaksa (K). Burdwan West Bengal	23°28' N+ 87°26' E	Lateritic	nil	4.80	0.43	5.25	4.45	5.05	.084
2. Jalpaiguri (J) West Bengal	26°30' N+ 88°45' E	Forest Dooars region	„	5.20	1.55	2.14	2.75	3.64	0.21
3. Thimpoo (T) Bhutan	27°30' N+ 89°30' E	Hilly Forest	„	5.80	1.72	11.45	3.80	4.65	0.13
4. Mohammed Bazar (M) Birbhum West Bengal	24°2' N+ 87°2' E	Lateritic	„	6.15	0.52	10.35	3.05	4.35	0.076

TABLE 2—CHANGE IN COMPOSITION OF IRON PHOSPHATE FE-P (A) IN

Buffer pH		(a) Buffer systems			Probable reactions	
		Fe ₂ O ₃ mole %	P ₂ O ₅ mole %	Fe ₂ O ₃ P ₂ O ₅		
1.	Untreated Fe-P(A)	0.18	0.18	1.00	Fe ₂ O ₃ + P ₂ O ₅ + 4H ₂ O → 2FePO ₄ ·2H ₂ O [or 2Fe(OH) ₂ ·H ₂ PO ₄]	
2.	4.8	0.19	0.17	1.10	unchanged (—do—)	
3.	5.2	0.22	0.18	1.20	unchanged (—do—)	
4.	5.8	0.23	0.15	1.53	3Fe ₂ O ₃ + 2P ₂ O ₅ + 0H ₂ O → (H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ Fe-O-Fe(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ + 4Fe(OH) ₂ ·4FeO·OH + 4H ₂ O	
5.	6.2	0.24	0.16	1.50	—do—	
Soil		(b) Soil Systems			Probable reactions	
pH		Fe ₂ O ₃ mole %	P ₂ O ₅ mole %	Fe ₂ O ₃ P ₂ O ₅		
1.	K	4.8	0.18	0.18	1.00	Same as in (2) in Table 2 (a)
2.	J	5.2	0.22	0.17	1.29	Same as in (3) in Table 2 (a)
3.	T	5.8	0.24	0.16	1.50	Same as in (4) in Table 2 (a)
4.	M	6.15(≈6.2)	0.24	0.16	1.50	Same as in (5) in Table 2 (a)

TABLE 3—CHANGE IN COMPOSITION OF IRON PHOSPHATE FE-P (B) IN

Buffer pH		(a) Buffer systems			Probable reactions	
		Fe ₂ O ₃ mole %	P ₂ O ₅ mole %	Fe ₂ O ₃ P ₂ O ₅		
1.	Untreated	0.12	0.30	0.40	2Fe ₂ O ₃ + 5P ₂ O ₅ + 11H ₂ O → 2Fe(OH)(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ + 2Fe(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂	
2.	4.8	0.18	0.50	0.36	Fe ₂ O ₃ + 3P ₂ O ₅ + 6H ₂ O → 2Fe(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂	
3.	5.2	0.20	0.40	0.50	Fe ₂ O ₃ + 2P ₂ O ₅ + 4H ₂ O → (H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ -O-Fe(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂	
4.	5.8	0.21	0.28	0.75	(i) 2Fe ₂ O ₃ + 2P ₂ O ₅ + 7H ₂ O → (H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ Fe-O-Fe(H ₂ PO ₄) ₂ + 3Fe(OH) ₂ → 3FeO·OH + 3H ₂ O or (ii) Fe ₂ O ₃ + P ₂ O ₅ + 4H ₂ O → 2FePO ₄ ·2H ₂ O [or 2Fe(OH) ₂ ·H ₂ PO ₄]	
5.	6.2	0.23	0.27	0.65	—do—	
Soil		(b) Soil systems			Probable reactions	
pH		Fe ₂ O ₃ mole %	P ₂ O ₅ mole %	Fe ₂ O ₃ P ₂ O ₅		
1.	K	4.8	0.20	0.67	0.34	Same as in (2) in Table 3 (a)
2.	J	5.2	0.22	0.43	0.51	Same as in (3) in Table 3 (a)
3.	T	5.8	0.23	0.27	0.85	Same as in (4) in Table 3 (a)
4.	M	6.5	(≈6.2) 0.24	0.24	1.00	Same as in (5) in Table 3 (a)

Fig. 1. Change in composition of Fe-P systems in buffer and soil systems.

○—Buffer system
●—Soil system

Results and Discussion

It can be observed from the tables that in case of the hydrated ferric phosphate purchased the Fe_2O_3/P_2O_5 ratios increased from 1.1 to 1.53 and for the prepared basic ferric phosphate the values changed from 0.36 to 0.85 in buffer systems at different pH. The probable chemical reactions occurring in such changes are given in the respective tables. Table 3 also indicate a more or less similar rise with such iron phosphates in Fe_2O_3/P_2O_5 ratio with K, J, T & M soils as in case of buffer systems.

In case of soils, however, in general sharper changes in Fe_2O_3/P_2O_5 ratios than in buffer system were observed. These changes are probably influenced by the content of soluble phosphates aluminium, iron etc. present in such soils. The results indicate that basic (hydroxy) phosphates are more susceptible to chemical change than the more stable $FePO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ or $Fe(OH)_2 \cdot H_2PO_4$. Basic phosphates ultimately converted to $FePO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$.

The changes in chemical composition probably associated with hydrolysis reactions, and exchange reactions of acid radical $H_2PO_4^-$ ion for OH groups; followed by condensation process leading to products of continuously increasing complexity and removal of H_3PO_4 molecules from cellophane bags. Such process can be considered by assuming the properties of $H_2PO_4^-$ to be similar to ClO_4^- or NO_3^- as all these are weak ligands in the pH 5-0 to 7-0 and susceptible to ionization at least partly as in case of $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ or $Fe(NO_3)_3$ (Remy⁸).

The following reactions may occur :

Hydrolysis products of this kind can exist in equilibrium with the normal salts (or its ions) even in relatively strongly acidic condition. With decreasing H^+ ion concentration, the equilibria may undergo a continuous displacement in the direction of further increase in the particle size i.e. colloidal dispersion until these particles undergo conversion into pure iron hydroxide $FeO.OH$, by elimination of the last acidic groups. Ultimately, however, unless the solutions are strongly acidic iron hydroxides may be deposited as the stable and product of hydrolysis in the form of $FeO.OH$, goethite. However, such hydrolysis equilibria can be reached only very slowly hydrolysis equilibria after in course of month.

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